

THE ROLE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN GLOBAL TRADE

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Annotation: This article talks about how the digital economy affects trade in different countries. The digitalization of the economy is growing rapidly, and the digital space is becoming a key area of global trade. The emergence of new formats and opportunities for international business through digitalization, the expansion of cross-border trade and invisible employment, as well as the reduction of cross-border and domestic operations in a globalized digital environment.

Key words: Digital economy, digitalization, globalization, world trade, technology, transformation, data flow, cross-border trade.

Introduction

Recently, one can find the effects of digitalization in all areas of economic activity, including global trade. World trade plays a key role in the global economy, affecting many aspects:

1. Economic Growth: Trade promotes economic growth by stimulating production, investment and innovation. Open markets allow countries to specialize in the production of goods and services in which they have a competitive advantage.

2. Job Creation: Global trade creates jobs through exports, imports and related activities in logistics, transport and trade.

3. Increased consumer choice: Through trade, consumers have access to a wide range of goods and services at competitive prices, which increases their wealth and improves their quality of life.

4. Technological transitions: Global trade facilitates the transfer of technology and knowledge between countries, which can contribute to their technological development and modernization.

5. Geopolitical Stability: Trade can help strengthen international relations and cooperation between countries, which contributes to geopolitical stability.

6. Poverty reduction: World trade can help reduce poverty by creating opportunities for economic growth and increased incomes.

Research methodology

In the textbook “Blockchain Technologies in the Digital Economy,” written by academician S. Gulomov and others, the concept of the digital economy was defined as follows: “The digital economy (electronic) is an economy characterized by maximum satisfaction of the needs of all participants through the use of information, including personal information. This may be due to the development of information, communication and financial technologies, as well as the openness of the infrastructure, ensuring the full interaction of all economic entities in a hybrid world - the creation of goods and services, objects and entities in the process of distribution, exchange and consumption.” According to Doctor of Economic Sciences S. Mustafakulov, the digital economy is an activity that is considered as the main factor in the production of digital data, which can significantly increase the efficiency of storage, sales and delivery of a number of industries, technologies, equipment, goods and services based on the use of the results of technological analysis and processing large volumes of data.

Analyzes and results

Today, the main question of the research is the scientific study of the patterns, trends and opportunities for the development of the digital economy in the conditions of Uzbekistan, including its use in international trade, in particular the level of penetration of information technologies in various fields. foreign economic activity. The development and prospects of our country, the success of large-scale reforms in our country are directly related to the introduction of innovations into our national economy. Therefore, it is important to improve the digital economy in foreign trade, scientific and practical study of its economic, political, social and legal framework. The research work used methods such as observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, induction and deduction.

By studying data from a survey of senior executives conducted by WEF experts in September 2015 on expected changes in the strategy and development of leading companies due to digitalization, important conclusions could be drawn. Here are some interesting results from this survey: - 88% of auto manufacturing respondents believe that by 2030, at least one of the largest automakers will generate more revenue from online sales of transportation information and services than from sales of vehicles and parts ; - 70% of representatives of companies providing various professional services believe that by 2025 digital solutions will generate more income than services provided directly by specialists;

-50% of representatives of the media and news agencies believe that by 2025, 90% of all news received by the population will be provided by computers; - 92% of representatives of the banking sector and stock market believe that by 2030, distributed ledger technology will become one of the key elements of the global financial system; - 50% of surveyed institutional investors and representatives of independent funds believe that by 2025, the majority of financial agreements and related document management will be carried out using blockchain architecture. A World Bank study entitled “Digital Dividends” shows how relevant and important

the digital economy is to economic development. In particular, increasing Internet speed by 10 percent will increase the country's GDP. In developed countries the rate is 1.21 percent, while in developing countries it is 1.38 percent. This means that if Internet speed doubles, GDP could also increase by about 15 percent. The concept of distributed production, which is an alternative to traditional economic globalization, and its principles based on the international division of labor, natural, relative and competitive advantages that countries have, are of great interest today. The main idea of this concept is to make the process of creating new values more efficient, taking into account their interests and local conditions, bringing production closer to the buyer/consumer, participating in the development of product design and other parameters. This reduces the time spent on the production process and its cost, significantly increasing adaptability to customer requirements. For example, the entire project could rely on a network of decentralized 3D printers and IT systems connected to manufacturing company systems through soft computing. Support chains are increasingly sharing electronic messages and data transfers. Instead of a traditional support system, fast and mobile networks of many participants are formed, which interact in real time based on digital technologies. Innovative business models and technological advances are creating new opportunities to increase efficiency and reduce costs in the sale of goods and services. Consequently, the growing process of digitalization can lead to qualitative changes in all areas of domestic and foreign economic activity. Conceptual insights, statistical methods and measurements in the field of the digital economy are not yet fully developed, but sufficient data have been collected to draw preliminary conclusions in certain areas. Digitalization of the economy creates additional opportunities to increase its growth and efficiency. A report on the digital economy, commissioned by the UK government in March 2016, noted that by fully harnessing the power of digitalization, the country's gross domestic product could grow by an average of 0.4

to 0.7 percent faster over the past decade. The basis of modern changes in the global economy and international trade is, on the one hand, the development and improvement of information technologies, filling the national economy with ICT goods and services, and on the other, the availability of mobile communications and the Internet.

The prospects for digital globalization are important for developing countries. In 2015, 70 percent of all Internet users in the world were in developing countries and countries with economies in transition, including 705 million in China, 333 million in India, 120 million in Brazil, 104 million in Russia, 87 million in Nigeria, 72 million in Mexico (for information: in the USA 242 million, in Japan - 118 million, in Germany - 72 million, in the UK - 59 million). Of the 750 million people who used the Internet for the first time between 2012 and 2015, about 90 percent were from developing countries, including 300 million from India and China. However, according to UNCTAD experts, online trade volumes in developing countries remain low. It should also be noted that countries such as China and South Korea have their own large e-commerce platforms and modern supply chain logistics systems, and the number of Internet users who buy or order goods and services online is growing every day. A new phenomenon emerging from the synthesis of digitalization and globalization, global online platforms are projected to contribute \$2.7 trillion to global GDP by 2025, create 72 million new jobs and improve economic outcomes for 540 million people.

Conclusion

The digital economy has a significant impact on global trade. Digitalization is the next stage in the development of global trade. Its impact on global trade lies in the emergence and spread of new digital technologies, the growth and strengthening of digital platforms, and the increase in the number of digital transactions. Online

platforms and e-commerce allow companies to easily reach international customers without significant investment in physical infrastructure.

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